

ANALYSIS OF STRUCTURAL AND SEMANTIC FEATURES OF COMPOUND WORDS IN UZBEK

Orziqulova Gulnoza Maxmudjon qizi

gulnozaorzikulova@gmail.com

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Abstract: The purpose of this study is to analyze the structural semantic peculiarities of Uzbek compound words. In addition, it is very important to study endocentricity and exocentricity of compounding in Uzbek. Its primary objective is to analyse with the brief examples of unknown components of the topic.

Keywords: compound words, endocentricity and exocentricity, compound nouns, compound verbs, compound adjectives.

When Uzbek compound words are analysed, it has not been investigated the exocentric features of compounding yet. The main reason is that, most compound words are endocentric due to its meaning. All Uzbek compound words have got the same meanings: both subordinating and the governor. As a clear example, *mehmonxona* – when it is separated into *mehmon* refers to guest and *xona* expresses a room. Based on Madaliyev’s book entitled “The dictionary of modern Uzbek compound words”, the semantic features of compounds have clearly represented. As he noted, he collected 30 thousand compounds on this book. In most productive source, most compounds have been met in biology and their phonetic versions have been outlined. Almost all Uzbek compound words are endocentric: *ko’zoynak*, *bilaguzuk*, *uchburchak*, *atirgul*, *bo’tako’z*, *nomozshomgul*, *mehmondo’st*, *balandparvoz*, *erksevar*.

According to the structural point of compounding in Uzbek, compound words are mostly appeared in three parts of compound nouns, compound verbs and compound adjectives.

1- Compound nouns

a. ***belbog’*** (*girdle- eng, gaine- fr*) consists of two lexemes, *bel- noun + bog’-noun = belbog’*. It is a national Uzbek cloth. Both words are used independently as a word.

b. ***bolaxona*** (*balcony – eng, jardin d’enfant- fr*) includes two free morphemes: *bola- noun + xona- noun = bolaxona*. It is an extra place for young children. Both of them stand alone as a word.

c. ***molqo’ra*** (*cowshed- eng, ètable – fr*) contains two lexemes: *mol- noun + qo’ra -noun = molqo’ra*. It is a place like barn which cows, horses and sheep keep. These words are free morphemes.

d. **qirqog'ayni** (*millet- eng, mille- fr*) consists of two free morphemes: *qirq-* numeral + *og'ayni*= *qirqog'ayni*. It is an insect. The words presented express the meaning alone.

e. **qo'lyozma** (*handwriting – eng, l'écriture- fr*)- includes two free morphemes: *qo'l-* noun + *yozma-* noun= *qo'lyozma*. It is a written sentence or work by hand.

f. **kuldon** (*ashtray- eng, cendrier- fr*)- contains two lexemes: *kul – noun* + *don* +suffix= *kuldon*. The noun *kul* is a free morpheme while suffix *don* is a bound morpheme.

2- Compound adjective

a. **balandbo'yli** (*tall- eng, haut- fr*)- is a compound adjective that includes two free morphemes and a suffix : *baland-* adjective + *bo'y-* noun + *li-* suffix= *balandbo'yli*.

b. **balandposhnali** (*high heel- eng, talons hauts- fr*)- consists of two free morphemes and a suffix: *baland-* adjective + *poshna-* noun + *li-* suffix= *balandposhnali*.

c. **kitobsevar** (*bibliophile in both English and French*) contains two independent morphemes that stand alone as a word but a suffix does not express the meaning. Its morphological process is *kitob-* noun + *sev-* verb+ *ar-* suffix= *kitobsevar*

3- Compound verbs

1. **olib kelmoq**(*bring in eng, prendre – fr*) is a compound verb that contains two free morphemes. These words stand alone and its morphological structure is *olib-* verb+ *kel* + verb= *olib kel*.

2. **yozib qo'ymoq-** (*put in eng, exprimer- fr*) consists of two free morphemes that express the meaning and its morphological process is *yoz-* verb and *qo'y-* verb.

3. **ushlab turmoq**(*hold in eng, tenir-fr*) is a compound verb and its morphological process is *ushla-* verb, *tur-*verb= *ushlab tur*. Both of them are free morphemes that represent the meaning.

In Uzbek, compound words are additionally divided into:

1) compatibility of ingredients: *wedding, book-loving, worldview*.

2) as a result of adaptation and connection of the owner and the cut: *the bride, the bridesmaids, the bridesmaids (ceremonies)*.

When it comes to endocentric features of compound words are identified and used on the target language. In Uzbek the endocentric compound words almost consist of compounding process.

1. *Yaqinda u “Jonatan Livingston laqabli **baliqchi qush**” asarini o’qidi.*

In the context, *baliqchi qush* (*seagull*) is a compound noun that has two words with similar grammatical categories as their components. *Baliqchi* is a fisherman and *qush* is a bird. In the sentence, both words are understood the meaning easily so, it is a endocentric compound word.

2. *Uzumlar qiyg’os pishibdi, uning bargini kesish uchun **tokqaychini** olib kel.*

The compound noun *tokqaychi* (*scissors for grape leaves*) is the same grammatical categories that *tok* is another name of grape in Uzbek, *qaychi* is a tool for cutting. Thus, it is an endocentric compound that express the meaning.

3. ***Temiryo’llar** uzoq manzilga boshlaydi.*

In the sentence, *temiryo’l*(*railway*) is a compound noun that express the meaning separately. Therefore, it is an endocentric noun. *Temir* is a comparison of rail and *yo’l* is directly understood way.

In some cases, a number of Uzbek linguists considered that exocentricity is not a phenomenon for Turkish languages, however, there are some words that does not represent the meaning separately. The followings are the examples of our description:

a. ***Beshiktebratar**shunday hashorotki, biz uni beozor hisoblasakda ularning inson sog’ligi uchun xavfli tomonlari bor.*

The compound noun *beshiktebratar*(*European mantis*)has two words with different grammatical categories: noun and verb. The noun *beshik* in this context is a furniture for babies while the verb *tebratmoq* means shaking or moving. *beshiktebratar*, however, does not mean shaking the cradle but it refers an insect mostly live in Europe. So, *beshiktebratar* is grouped to the exocentric compounds as the meaning cannot be predicted from the words.

b. ***Xonqizilar** ko’pincha gul va daraxtlar shoxiga qo’nadi.*

The compound noun *xonqizi*(*ladybird*)contains two words with different grammatical categories: noun and noun. The noun *xon* in this context is a king in Asia *qiz* means a daughter or a girl. *Xonqizi* ,however, does not mean a daughter of a king or a princess but it refers an insect that has a red surface and black spots on the body.. So, *xonqizi* is grouped to the exocentric compounds as the meaning cannot be predicted from the words *xon* and *qizi*.

c. *Tunda **boyo’g’lining** mungli tovush yangrab turar edi.*

The compound noun *boyo’g’li*(*owl*)consists of two words with different grammatical categories: adjective and noun. The adjective *boy* in this context means rich or wealthy while the noun *o’g’li* is a son. Nevertheless, *boyo’g’li* does

not mean the son of rich person but it refers a bird that sings at night. So, boyo'g'li is regarded as the exocentric compounds as the meaning cannot be predicted.

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